

Determining Factors of the Use of Active Public Space: A Survey on the Urban Corridors of Ijen Boulevard and Jakarta Street

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Abstract— *Public space is a place for which people carry out their activities. Urban public space represents the desire of urban communities to interact with the surroundings. The development of public space use is adjusted to the increase of public activities in terms of type and intensity. Many people use streets and parks to express their activities as they are types of open and easily accessible public spaces.*

This study aimed to investigate the factors affecting the use of active public space, namely the corridors of Ijen and Jakarta street, and the quality of the two public spaces analyzed by using the Exploratory Factor Analysis. The variables studied were the characteristics of environmental psychology; the activities/utilization of each active public space and the preferences of the users. It was found that there were 7 (seven) factors affecting the use of active public space at the Ijen Boulevard and 3 (three) factors affecting the use of active public space at the Jakarta street. The active public space at Ijen boulevard managed to meet three of the public space criteria, including Meaningful, Responsive and Democratic. On the other hand, active public space at the Jakarta street fulfilled one criterion of public space, which was Democratic.

Keywords— *Urban activities, use of public space, exploratory factor analysis.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Public space is a place provided for the community for doing their activities, including recreational and entertainment activities such as walking, taking breaks, relaxing, or social activities such as gatherings, official ceremonies, and sometimes, trading. Urban public space represents the desire of urban communities to interact with the surrounding environment (Edi, 2013). Public spaces can be green spaces, such as parks and gardens, play areas, sports facilities, and green corridors. Public spaces can also be civil spaces such as pedestrian streets and sports facilities. In an urban area, public open space has a recreational effect for the community in the midst of the busy city life.

The Ijen Boulevard corridor is an integrated design between the park and the residential area with the concept of colonial architecture. This corridor is one of the main streets in Malang City which was originally known as the elite residential of the Dutch. Ijen Boulevard extends from north to south with the intersection of the road completed neatly and equipped with a park. The active public space (park) is also present in the middle as the separator of the opposite pathway. The city forest on the Jakarta street corridor has now turned into an active public space. The park located on the Jakarta street corridor also has a special feature in the lighting system

which is inspired by the Fireflies. The concept of this park is different from some thematic parks that have been built, one of which is its uniqueness as it is located in the middle of the street corridor.

The development of public space utilization goes hand in hand with the increase of the intensity and the type of activities. The lifestyle changes of the community in filling their spare time and entertainment also affect the use of public space. Many people use the street or park to express their activities as they are kinds of public spaces that are open and easily accessible by the community.

Generally, the city parks in Malang are mostly located in the spots that have been used for public open spaces from the first place, meanwhile, the parks at the corridor of Ijen and Jakarta Street were originally passive public spaces equipped with only their aesthetic elements and were not supporting the activities to be done in it. Nowadays, the use of public space for activities and interaction has become a phenomenon and also has a positive response, hence the government of Malang City did some renovations toward the parks. This was eventually triggered a significant change in utilization of the parks, hence it also requires further evaluation.

The increasing number of public activity carried out in the public spaces indicates a change of the public space utilization by the users. This demonstrates a high desire of the community toward the availability of public spaces that are easily accessible. Various changes in urban design in a certain region are indirectly caused by the changes that motivate people to do their activities. Activities that are done in public space arise because the public space itself is convenient and can accommodate the activities of the people.

In terms of space utilization, the community uses these public spaces for various activities, such as exercising, relaxing, and social politics activities besides being used according to its main purpose. Some parts of the road and park corridors are also used for informal sector activities at particular times and also by the community for other types of activities.

Based on this phenomenon, it is necessary to investigate the factors that influence the utilization of public space in Malang City in terms of the characteristics and preferences of current users. Analysis on the factors of public space utilization in this study was carried out using Exploratory Factor Analysis.

Fig. 1. Research Location 1 (Ijen Boulevard Park)

Fig. 2. Research Location 2 (Jakarta Street Park)

II. METHOD

The stages of this study are identifying the factors that influence the use of active public space located at the corridors of Ijen boulevard and Jakarta street, and then analyzing whether or not the parks meet the requirements of public spaces quality. The variables studied in this research are based on the Theory of Environmental Psychology and considering the condition of public spaces where the data are collected. The instrument used for data collection is the questionnaire.

The method of data analysis implemented was the Exploratory Factor Analysis, which is used to determine the factors affecting the utilization of public space and then grouped based on the main criteria. Exploratory factor analysis is used in a condition where the formation of new latent

variables is random, then, the results of the analysis are interpreted according to the factors or components or constructs formed. Data analysis was carried out using the SPSS program.

The determination of sample number is done by using the Linear time function method since there was no data on the visitors of the corridors of Ijen and Jakarta street. Linear time function is a technique of determining the number of samples based on the estimated time constraints (Sari, 1993). The formula of Linear time function is:

$$n = \frac{T - t_0}{t_1}$$

- n = The number of samples
- T = Available time for a survey
- t0 = Time-constat of survey duration
- t1 = Time use for sampling

Therefore, the sample size calculation is:

$$T = 7 \text{ days} \times 24 \text{ hours/day} = 168$$

$$t_0 = 10 \text{ hours/day} \times 7 \text{ days} = 70$$

$$t_1 = 0,25 \text{ hour} \times 7 \text{ days} = 1,75$$

$$n = \frac{168 - 70}{1,75} = 128 \text{ Respondents}$$

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

In the Exploratory Factor Analysis, there are 8 (eight) variables that correlate with each other and group into one component. In this case, one component might have a significant relationship between variables but with relatively weak correlation with other component variables.

The Description of Activity in the Active Public Space at Ijen Boulevard

The character of users' activities in active public space on the Ijen Boulevard corridor can be seen from the data obtained from the questionnaires distributed to 128 respondents. The data include the type of activity, then the data was linked to the number of each activity based on the gender of respondents.

TABLE I. The Characteristics of Activity in the Active Public Space at Ijen Boulevard

Activity		Gender		Total
		Male	Female	
Sport	Count	8	1	9
	% of Total	6.3%	0.8%	7.0%
Short Break	Count	18	9	27
	% of Total	14.1%	7.0%	21.1%
Gathering	Count	27	23	50
	% of Total	21.1%	18.0%	39.1%
Waiting	Count	16	12	28
	% of Total	12.5%	9.4%	21.9%
Other	Count	9	5	14
	% of Total	7.0%	3.9%	10.9%
Total	Count	78	50	128
	% of Total	60.9%	39.1%	100.0%
<i>Average percentage</i>		12.2%	7.8%	

Source: Data Analysis, 2019

The type of activity with a percentage (%) more than the average percentage of each sex is expressed as the dominant

type of activity. The dominant activities in male respondents were gathering and taking a short break. On the other hand, the dominant activities in female respondents were gathering and waiting (for someone or have an appointment).

The Description of Activity in The Active Public Space at Jakarta Street

Table II shows a description of activities carried out by the community in utilizing active public space at the Jakarta street corridor. Data were obtained from 128 respondents.

TABLE II. The Characteristics of Activity in the Active Public Space at Jakarta Street

Activity		Gender		Total
		Male	Female	
Sport	Count	13	6	19
	% of Total	10.2%	4.7%	14.8%
Short Break	Count	23	16	39
	% of Total	18.0%	12.5%	30.5%
Gathering	Count	21	26	47
	% of Total	16.4%	20.3%	36.7%
Waiting	Count	7	5	12
	% of Total	5.5%	3.9%	9.4%
Other	Count	7	4	11
	% of Total	5.5%	3.1%	8.6%
Total	Count	71	57	128
	% of Total	55.5%	44.5%	100.0%
Average percentage		11.1%	8.9%	

Source: Data Analysis, 2019

Based on table II, it can be seen that the dominant activities in both male and female respondents were taking a short break and gathering.

The Factors of the Use of Active Public Space at Ijen Boulevard

These are the results of the Exploratory Factor Analysis on the data of active public space utilization on Ijen Boulevard.

TABLE III. The Result of MSA Score - Stage 1

Anti-image Correlation	Anti-image Matrices							
	X1	X2	X3	X4	X5	X6	X7	X8
X1	.426*	-.113	.093	-.103	-.122	.204	.034	.004
X2	-.113	.544*	.050	-.027	-.016	-.069	.015	-.049
X3	.093	.050	.591*	.071	.020	.074	-.039	-.038
X4	-.103	-.027	.071	.516*	.009	-.063	.019	-.043
X5	-.122	-.016	.020	.009	.451*	-.227	.015	.022
X6	.204	-.069	.074	-.063	-.227	.440*	.004	.054
X7	.034	.015	-.039	.019	.015	.004	.591*	.012
X8	.004	-.049	-.038	-.043	.022	.054	.012	.426*

Source: Data Analysis, 2019

The result of the MSA (Measures of Sampling Adequacy) score on stage 1 on the user preferences of the corridor park at Ijen Boulevard shows that indicators X1, X5, and X6 had scores less than 0.50. Thus, adjustments are needed to be made by eliminating the indicator with the lowest MSA value (X1, 0.426) and then reprocessing the Factor analysis.

TABLE IV. The Result of KMO Score - Stage 1

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.472
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	23.224
	df	28
	Sig.	.722

Source: Data Analysis, 2019

Stage 1 of the KMO (Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin) score on the preferences of public space user at Ijen Boulevard demonstrates the score of 0.491 (< 0.50). This indicates that the adjustment needs to be made.

TABLE V. The Result of MSA Score – Stage 2

Anti-image Correlation	Anti-image Matrices						
	X2	X3	X4	X5	X6	X7	X8
X2	.620*	.056	-.039	-.030	-.041	.019	.050
X3	.056	.596*	.079	.027	.061	-.041	-.038
X4	-.039	.079	.590*	-.004	-.037	.014	.046
X5	-.030	.027	-.004	.536*	-.204	.020	.023
X6	-.041	.061	-.037	-.204	.543*	-.006	.055
X7	.019	-.041	.014	.020	-.006	.539*	.012
X8	.050	-.038	.046	.023	.055	.012	.614*

Source: Data Analysis, 2019

The MSA (Measures of Sampling Adequacy) score on stage 2 on the user preferences of the public space at Ijen Boulevard demonstrates that all indicators had the values greater than 0.50. Therefore, the requirement for Factor analysis based on the MSA value was fulfilled.

TABLE VI. The Result of KMO Score - Stage 2

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.563
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	10.814
	df	21
	Sig.	.966

Source: Data Analysis, 2019

The result of the KMO (Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin) value stage 2 on the public space users of corridor park at Ijen Boulevard shows a value of 0.563 (> 0.50), hence the requirement for factor analysis based on the KMO value has been fulfilled.

TABLE VII. Loading Factor – Stage 2

	Rotated Component Matrix ^a		
	Component		
	1	2	3
X2		.484	
X3		-.569	
X4		.619	
X5	.793		
X6	.747		
X7			.871
X8			-.447

Source: Data Analysis, 2019

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization. ^a

a. Rotation converged in 4 iterations.

Essentially, a public space must have 3 criteria. They are Meaningful, which means that the public space must provide the purpose and meaning to the local community individually or in groups; Responsive, which means that it is responsive to all user desires and can accommodate activities carried out in the public space; and Democratic, which means that the public space can accommodate the users of all layers of society without any discrimination. Based on the result of Factor analysis, it was found that the elements can be grouped into a smaller group. In this study, the major factors as the result of the elements grouping are Meaningful, Responsive and Democratic.

The result of Factor analysis demonstrates the determining factors of the use of public space which in this case is the corridor park at Ijen Boulevard. It was found that the variable X2 (The convenience in staying or doing the activities in public space), X3 (The convenience in using public space) and X4 (The setting of site elements) can be combined into 1 factor, with the loading factors value in Component 2. Furthermore, the variables of X5 (The user experience of direct interaction) and X6 (Active engagement with the area) can be combined into 1 factor, with the value of loading factors in Component 1. The variable of X7 (The desire for experience and new scenery) and X8 (Facility and utility) can be combined into 1 factor, with the value of loading factors in the column of Component 3.

Fig. 3. The Criteria of Public Space (Corridor Park) at Ijen Boulevard

The public park on the corridor of Ijen boulevard met the overall criteria of public space, including:

- **Meaningful** (can provide the purpose and meaning to the local community individually or in groups). In this case, it is associated with the chosen factor that the Ijen corridor park can provide experience in direct interaction and bring out the element of active engagement between users and the area. In other words, there is an emotional bond between the users and the public space.
- **Responsive** (responsive to all user desires and can accommodate activities carried out in the public space). This is associated with the chosen factor that the Ijen corridor park can provide the users' desire for the new experiences and scenery as well as the complete facility and utility. The park is well designed and managed by considering the interests of its users.
- **Democratic** (can accommodate the users of all layers of society without any discrimination). This is linked to the chosen factor that the Ijen corridor park is able to provide comfort in staying at the public space, comfort in utilizing public space, and the well setting of site elements. This reflects that the rights of public space users have been fulfilled and protected so that they are free to express themselves. The freedom of expression in this context is certainly still within the boundaries as the use of public space is also requires the tolerance between users.

The Factors of the Use of Active Public Space at Ijen Boulevard

This section explains the result of the Exploratory Factor Analysis on the public space use on the Jakarta street corridor.

TABLE VIII. The Result of MSA Score – Stage 1

Anti-image Correlation	Anti-image Matrices							
	X1	X2	X3	X4	X5	X6	X7	X8
X1	.422*	-.066	.137	-.236	.294	.148	.012	-.108
X2	-.066	.491*	-.196	-.064	-.117	-.106	.087	.041
X3	.137	-.196	.461*	-.102	.177	-.007	.138	.019
X4	-.236	-.064	-.102	.418*	-.068	-.057	-.128	.028
X5	.294	-.117	.177	-.068	.438*	.097	-.048	-.058
X6	.148	-.106	-.007	-.057	.097	.422*	-.089	.060
X7	.012	.087	.138	-.128	-.048	-.089	.431*	.049
X8	-.108	.041	.019	.028	-.058	.060	.049	.520*

Source: Data Analysis, 2019

The result of the MSA (Measures of Sampling Adequacy) scoring on stage 1 on the user preferences of public space on the Jakarta street corridor shows that indicators X1, X2, X3, X4, X5, X6, and X7 have the score less than 0.50. Therefore, the adjustment needs to be made by eliminating the indicator with the lowest MSA score (X4, 0.418) and then reprocess the Factor analysis.

TABLE IX. The Result of KMO – Stage 1

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.	.444	
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	42.610
	df	28
	Sig.	.038

Source: Data Analysis, 2019

The result of stage 1 KMO (Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin) score on the factor of users preference toward the Jakarta street corridor demonstrates the score of 0.444 and less than 0.50, thus the adjustment needs to be made.

TABLE X. The Result of MSA Score – Stage 2

Anti-image Correlation	Anti-image Matrices							
	X1	X2	X3	X5	X6	X7	X8	
X1	.427*	-.084	.117	.287	.139	-.019	-.104	
X2	-.084	.484*	.191	-.122	-.110	.080	.043	
X3	.117	.191	.509*	.172	-.013	.127	.022	
X5	.287	-.122	.172	.454*	.093	-.057	-.036	
X6	.139	-.110	-.013	.093	.428*	-.098	.062	
X7	-.019	.080	.127	-.057	-.098	.450*	.053	
X8	-.104	.043	.022	-.036	.062	.053	.527*	

Source: Data Analysis, 2019

The score of MSA (Measures of Sampling Adequacy) stage 2 on the user preferences of the public space on the Jakarta street corridor shows that indicators X1, X2, X5, X6, and X7 were less than 0.50. Therefore, the adjustments need to be done by eliminating the indicator with the lowest MSA score (X1, 0.427) and then reprocess the Factor analysis.

TABLE XI. The Result of KMO – Stage 2

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.	.463	
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	32.442
	df	21
	Sig.	.053

Source: Data Analysis, 2019

The result of the stage 2 KMO (Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin) score on the factor of users preference toward the Jakarta street corridor demonstrates a score of 0.463 (< 0.50), thus the adjustment need to be made.

TABEL XII. The Result of MSA – Stage 3

Anti-image Correlation	Anti-image Matrices					
	X2	X3	X5	X6	X7	X8
X2	.507 ^a	.203	-.102	-.099	.078	.035
X3	.203	.532 ^a	.145	-.030	.130	.035
X5	-.102	.145	.588 ^a	.056	-.054	-.006
X6	-.099	-.030	.056	.462 ^a	-.096	.078
X7	.078	.130	-.054	-.096	.454 ^a	.052
X8	.035	.035	-.006	.078	.052	.518 ^a

Source: Data Analysis, 2019

The score of MSA (Measures of Sampling Adequacy) stage 3 on the user preferences of the public space on the Jakarta street corridor shows that indicators X1, X2, X5, X6, and X7 were still less than 0.50. Thus, the adjustment needs to be done by eliminating the indicator with the lowest MSA score (X7, 0.454) and then reprocess the Factor analysis.

TABEL XIII. The Result of KMO Score – Stage 3

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.	.518	
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	17.557
	df	15
	Sig.	.287

Source: Data Analysis, 2019

The result of the KMO (Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin) scores stage 3 on the user preferences of the public space on the Jakarta street corridor shows a value of 0.518 (> 0.50), hence the requirement for factor analysis based on the KMO score has been fulfilled.

TABEL XIV. The Result of MSA Score - Stage 4

Anti-image Correlation	Anti-image Matrices				
	X2	X3	X5	X6	X8
X2	.549 ^a	.195	-.099	-.092	.031
X3	.195	.550 ^a	.154	-.018	.029
X5	-.099	.154	.581 ^a	.051	-.004
X6	-.092	-.018	.051	.481 ^a	.083
X8	.031	.029	-.004	.083	.515 ^a

Source: Data Analysis, 2019

The score of MSA (Measures of Sampling Adequacy) stage 4 on the user preferences of the public space on the Jakarta street corridor shows that indicator X6 had a score of 0.481 (< 0.50). Therefore, the indicator X6 must be eliminated and the Factor analysis must be reprocessed.

TABEL XV. The Result of KMO Score – Stage 4

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.	.549	
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	13.293
	df	10
	Sig.	.208

Source: Data Analysis, 2019

The result of the KMO (Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin) score stage 4 on the user preferences of the public space on the Jakarta street corridor shows a score of 0.549 (> 0.50), hence the

requirement for factor analysis based on the KMO score has been fulfilled. Furthermore, the result of MSA scoring on stage 5 is presented in the following table.

TABEL XVI. The Result of MSA Score- Stage 5

		Anti-image Matrices			
		X2	X3	X5	X8
Anti-image Covariance	X2	.945	.182	-.090	.038
	X3	.182	.931	.146	.029
	X5	-.090	.146	.960	-.008
	X8	.038	.029	-.008	.998
Anti-image Correlation	X2	.563 ^a	.194	-.094	.039
	X3	.194	.551 ^a	.155	.030
	X5	-.094	.155	.593 ^a	-.008
	X8	.039	.030	-.008	.406 ^a

Source: Data Analysis, 2019

The result of MSA scoring (Measures of Sampling Adequacy) stage 5 on the user preferences of the public space on the Jakarta street corridor shows that indicator X8 had a score of 0,406 (< 0.50). Therefore, the indicator X8 must be eliminated and the Factor analysis must be reprocessed.

TABEL XVII. The Result of KMO – Stage 5

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.	.563	
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	11.081
	df	6
	Sig.	.086

Source: Data Analysis, 2019

The result of the KMO (Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin) score stage 5 on the user's preferences of the public space on the Jakarta street corridor shows the score of 0.563 (> 0.50), hence the requirement for factor analysis based on the KMO score has been fulfilled.

TABEL XVIII. The Result of MSA Score – Stage 6

		Anti-image Matrices		
		X2	X3	X5
Anti-image Covariance	X2	.947	.182	-.090
	X3	.182	.932	.147
	X5	-.090	.147	.960
Anti-image Correlation	X2	.569 ^a	.193	-.094
	X3	.193	.554 ^a	.155
	X5	-.094	.155	.593 ^a

Source: Data Analysis, 2019

The result of MSA scoring (Measures of Sampling Adequacy) stage 6 on the user's preferences toward the public space on the Jakarta street corridor shows that all indicators had the scores greater than 0.50. Therefore, the requirement for factor analysis based on the MSA score has been fulfilled

TABEL XIX. The Result of KMO Score – Stage 6

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.	.568	
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	10.846
	df	3
	Sig.	.013

Source: Data Analysis, 2019

The result of the KMO (Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin) score stage 6 on the user preferences of the public space on the Jakarta

street corridor shows the score of 0.568 (> 0.50), hence the requirement for factor analysis based on the KMO score has been fulfilled. Furthermore, the result of the Loading factor on stage 6 is displayed by the following table.

TABLE XX. Hasil Loading Faktor Tahap 6

Component Matrix ^a	
Variable	Component
	1
X2	.668
X3	-.722
X5	.616

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis

a. 1 component extracted

Source: Data Analysis, 2019

In general, several factors or components can be grouped into smaller groups (Meaningful, Responsive and Democratic) with suitable criteria according to the literature review. The result of Factor analysis revealed that the variable X2 (the convenience in staying or doing the activities in public space), X3 (The convenience in using public space) and X5 (The user experience of the direct interaction) can be combined be 1 factor with the value of loading factor in Component 1

Fig. 4. The Criteria of Public Space (Corridor Park) at the Jakarta Street

Based on the results of the analysis, three of the nine research variables have been chosen to be the determining factors of the use of active public space at the Jakarta Street corridor. These three factors can be grouped again according to the fulfillment of the criteria for public space. It can be concluded that the Jakarta street corridor has fulfilled one of the three public space criteria set by Stephen Carr (1992), which was Democratic (can accommodate the users of all layers of society without any discrimination). This finding is associated with the chosen factor that the public space at the Jakarta street corridor is able to provide comfort for the users for staying and doing their activities. In addition, visitors also feel comfortable using public space, as well as feeling the experience of direct interaction. This indicates that the rights of public space users have been fulfilled and protected so that they are free to express themselves. The freedom of expression in this context is certainly within the boundaries as the use of public space is also requires the tolerance between users.

IV. CONCLUSION

Based on the findings, it can be concluded that:

1. The active public space on the Ijen Boulevard corridor is located in the middle of the city and complete with its constituent elements. This makes the public space convenient as a gathering point or a short break in the afternoon or evening. This also makes the two activities as the most dominant activities in terms of public space use.
2. The active public space in Jakarta street corridor is located in the middle of the education area of Malang City, complete with the constituent elements that make it convenient to be used as a gathering place and a short break in the afternoon or evening. In other words, the two activities are the most dominant types of activities in public space.
3. The results of the Factor analysis on the corridor of Ijen boulevard park indicated that the variables of the variable X2 (The convenience in staying or doing the activities in public space), X3 (The convenience in using public space) and X4 (The setting of site elements) can be combined into 1 factor, with the loading factors value in Component 2. Furthermore, the variables of X5 (The user experience of direct interaction) and X6 (Active engagement with the area) can be combined into 1 factor, with the value of loading factors in Component 1. The variable of X7 (The desire for experience and new scenery) and X8 (Facility and utility) can be combined into 1 factor, with the value of loading factors in Component 3.
4. The eight factors can be grouped again according to the fulfillment of the types of public space criteria. It can be concluded that the corridor of Ijen boulevard has fulfilled the overall criteria of public space based on Stephen Carr (1992). These criteria are Meaningful (can provide the purpose and meaning to the local community individually or in groups), Responsive (responsive to all user desires and can accommodate activities carried out in the public space) and Democratic (can accommodate the users of all layers of society without any discrimination).
5. The results of the Factor analysis on the corridor of Jakarta street demonstrated that the variable X2 (the convenience in staying or doing the activities in public space), X3 (The convenience in using public space) and X5 (The user experience of the direct interaction) can be combined be 1 factor with the value of loading factor in Component 1.
6. The three factors can be grouped again according to the fulfillment of the public space criteria. Finally, it can be concluded that Jakarta street park has fulfilled one criterion of public space criteria based on Stephen Carr (1992), namely Democratic (can accommodate the users of all layers of society without any discrimination).

V. SUGGESTION

In order to enhance the quality and usefulness of the active public spaces, the authors kindly suggest these recommendations:

1. The availability of public open space has become an important requirement in urban development for the sake

of sustainability of a comfortable and healthy life for the community. Thus, it is necessary to prioritize the provision of public space for urban communities. The availability of adequate public space can increase the comfort of the city community, and at the same time, attract the tourists.

2. Urban design will be better if it has a lot of public spaces for providing the comfortable, productive and sustainable space for the community.
3. The provision of public space must consider the criteria set by Stephen Carr (1992), including Meaningful (can provide the purpose and meaning to the local community individually or in groups), Responsive (responsive to all user desires and can accommodate activities carried out in the public space) and Democratic (can accommodate the users of all layers of society without any discrimination).

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